

ReNEW

D1.4 IWT Infrastructure Resilience
Interdependencies and Cascading
Effects Knowledge Graphs v1

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	Meaning
KG	Knowledge Graphs
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
GA	Grant Agreement
BN	Bayesian Networks
ATS	Autonomous Transportation Systems
GTFS	General Transit Feed Specification
KGNA	Knowledge Graphs-based Network Analysis
IW	Inland Waterways
SOTA	State Of The Art
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport

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1 Executive Summary

This document provides an overview of Task 1.2 on the development of the Ontology and Knowledge Graph (KG) for the ReNEW project. The primary goal of the task is to build systems and services around the Knowledge Graphs to utilise the results using AI & ML with iterative testing and selection of methods. This will facilitate the analysis of risks and cascading effects, evaluation of resilience, and optimisation of costs and efficiency. The KG's architecture is designed to model interactions and relationships between entities involved in studied system. This way the KG can be used to assist decision-making, enabling the review of simulations for hypothetical events, and acting to prevent or mitigate them. The KG uses various forms of data, including environmental conditions, operational requirements, and resilience framework strategies.

One of the key elements of the project is the incorporation of Probabilistic Digital Twins via Bayesian Networks, which offer substantial benefits in forecasting the system reactions to predicted and unexpected occurrences. This approach also allows for an update of the model with new data for more accurate estimation.

The document will further elaborate on the intricate details of Bayesian Networks and their application in diagnosis, reasoning, causal modelling, decision making under uncertainty, anomaly detection, automated insight, and prediction. The document will also provide a theoretical example of risk modelling using Bayesian Networks.

Leveraging the capacity of Knowledge Graphs and Network Analysis in capturing and modelling the real world relationships of a domain, Task 1.2 of Work package 1 aims to build a decision support system to optimise resilience using visualising, querying and simulating cascading effects.

2 Introduction

Task 1.2.1 focuses on the creation of an Ontology and Knowledge Graph (KG). This KG, although in principle a kind of database, is not just an assemblage of data, but rather a dynamic system built around the concept of resilience in Inland Water Transport (IWT) which models the relationship between infrastructures, environment, climate and operations.

The KG when fully implemented can enable a range of analyses, from risk and cascading effect assessments to resilience evaluations and cost and efficiency optimisations. It's a tool geared towards providing the most accurate and efficient outcomes given varying operational and environmental conditions.

This report will outline the current high-level architecture of the KG, discuss the role of Bayesian Networks in the development of Probabilistic Digital Twins, and explain how these technologies can be applied to improve resilience, efficiency, and decision-making in IWT. An illustrative example of risk modelling using Bayesian Networks is also included to help readers understand the practical applications of these theories.

2.1 Link to Project

ReNEW attempts to address the ever-increasing challenges associated with the operational resilience of IWT. The increasing level of variability, heterogeneity, and complexity of IWT systems adds to the system's climate change vulnerabilities and challenges its ability to react to severe predictable events and particularly to unexpected events. Inland ports located along inland waterways constitute efficient distribution hubs regulating various freight flows to cities, linked to global transport via seaport gateways making the resilience of IW ports particularly important.

Digitalisation is a fundamental enabler of smart solutions for sustainable transport that can support resilience and deliver economic, environmental, and societal benefits. Particularly important, from an IWT resilience perspective, is the improved interaction between infrastructure management systems and barge operations. Combining the technological advantages of digitalisation and automation, including autonomous barges and autonomous infrastructure interaction, provide economic benefits to revolutionise the future IWT system, whilst delivering climate-neutral and resilient IWT services.

A vital component for achieving digitisation in systems managed and operated by people, is the establishment of all the physical and non-physical infrastructures and processes in an integrated framework. Such activity enables the analysis of a dynamic response to disruptions, considering the engagement of multiple stakeholders and infrastructures. The processes can be automated and optimised utilising quantitative methods and algorithms for the smart, green, and resilient operation of IWT, especially considering risks and hazards caused by adverse events due to the climate crisis, and general network disruptions. To achieve this a semantic model and the Knowledge Graph for the

IWT infrastructure resources and topology is defined which is associated with the KPIs identified and prioritised based on input from the living labs.

2.2 Mapping the ReNEW Output

The following table (Table 1) maps the ReNEW’s Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work to perform.

Table 1: Adherence to ReNEW’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Deliverable D1.4 IWT infrastructure Resilience Interdependencies and Cascading Effects Knowledge Graphs v1		
Network resources Knowledge Graph semantic Framework. Infrastructure and mobile assets DSS Design, Specs and Proof of Concept Prototypes.		
Task T1.2 IWT infrastructure Resilience Interdependencies and Cascading Effects Knowledge Graphs		
Develop of Decision Support facilities, utilising quantitative methods and algorithms for the smart, green, and resilient operation of IWT, especially considering risks and hazards caused by adverse events due to the climate crisis, and general network disruptions. Address the IW stakeholder needs from the Living Labs, resulting strategies and optimised solutions for the available infrastructure and vessel transportation resources.		
ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter (s) and Description
ST1.2.1 IWT Network Resources Knowledge Graph	Create the semantic models and the Knowledge Graph for the IWT infrastructure resources and topology, defining the ReNEW ontology. Incorporate, map, and create the distributed repository resources employing a graphs database (triple-store or property graph, e.g., GraphDB, Neo4j) to store, process (semantically link and extend) and retrieve all concepts of the ReNEW models as defined in T1.1. Semantically capture the unique operational characteristics of the IWT network, e.g., seasonality in draught, topography, linked infrastructures, and cascading effects spreading between specific network locations, operational availability and capacity, multimodal nodes, and connections (i.e., transshipment) and environmental aspects and extreme weather vulnerability characteristics, of both terminal infrastructure and transportation resources for mitigation scenarios used for Decision	Chapter 3 Describes Ontologies and their applicability. Currently developed ontology with IWT resources

	<p>Support. Hence, the ReNEW Knowledge Graph will model and link available transportation resources (river and multimodal road and rail connections), and the linked infrastructures, capacities, vulnerabilities, and interconnections which eventually will be the basis of the cascading effects knowledge graph.</p>	
<p>ST1.2.2 Infrastructure life-cycle decision framework based on Resilience and Sustainability</p>	<p>Using open-source resources, configure a set of models and tools to support resilience and sustainability enhancement strategies, decisions, and operations, taking a graph theoretical approach. Consider operational service levels of IWT infrastructures and IW transportation against which resilience and sustainability can be benchmarked. Seek and model infrastructural resources interdependencies, assessing expected outcomes and impacts. Develop a multi-objective optimization model to balance maintenance policies throughout the rivers and infrastructure lifecycles also considering infrastructure resources deterioration, to support defined service levels of river navigability and operability, accounting for extreme weather events, risks, and hazards scenarios. The life-cycle optimisation model will be extended to consider budgetary constraints for technological and infrastructural interventions and stakeholder specific time horizons for optimal development strategies and investment prioritisation. Parametrise the decision environment for infrastructures defining the boundaries and options available, based on Living Labs use cases and perform probabilistic risk and safety analyses for reliability assessments of IWT infrastructure, including cascading effects for IW infrastructures, transportation facilities and services deployed.</p>	<p>Chapters 3 and 5</p>
<p>ST1.2.3 Routing and (re)Scheduling Decision Support to cater extreme events, risks, and hazards</p>	<p>Utilise the multimodal network representation of the Knowledge Graph and provide computational resources in the form of algorithms and services to capture, represent and produce solutions related to transportation resources optimal routing, rerouting, and scheduling in the view of extreme events. Improve resilience by identifying hinterland transshipment options, which in the view of emergencies have positive impacts on resilience, while they help increasing modal share and sustainability. Support mitigation strategies for the LLs considering barges autonomy and modular floating platform (WP2) enabled services. Create solution templates that model the structural and operational limitations of the IWT networks to optimally exploit and to improve configuration flexibility of transport based on enhanced fleet and terminal infrastructure utilization. Provide a DSS (a) to help defining a planning horizon for operations enabling the analysis of sudden changes in infrastructure availability and resilience assessment. (b) starting from the LLs use cases, to parametrise “failure and recovery” scenarios (i.e. incident rates, interdependencies) considering combinations of network components failing, (c) that includes algorithms to dynamically redistribute resources considering the transport demand, the peaks created by events, the unavailability of resources and the possible alternatives. (d) to graphically present the updated network status, and the network operations assessed within the planning horizon as compared to its baseline operation.</p>	<p>Chapters 4 talks about network analysis and probabilistic models for modelling risk events.</p>

2.3 Deliverable Structure

The deliverable structure aims to provide a comprehensive overview of fundamental concepts related to ontologies, Bayesian networks, and preliminary ontologies, while emphasising their potential application within the project's scope.

The "Introduction" section 2 establishes the context by linking the deliverable to the overall project goals and mapping its output to the ReNEW project's objectives. This helps readers understand the relevance and significance of the deliverable's contents.

The first major section, "Ontologies & Knowledge Graphs," introduces the basics of ontologies and their importance in representing knowledge and achieving semantic interoperability. It explains their role in the Inland Waterways Transportation (IWT) domain, supporting sustainable and resilient planning and decision-making. The subsection on "Preliminary Ontology for IWT" delves into the development of an initial ontology specific to IWT, describing the ontological hierarchy, entities, relations, and attributes that characterise the domain. Additionally, the deliverable discusses sustainability and resilience indicators, showcasing their integration into the ontology to support domain-specific analysis.

In the next section, "Network Analysis and Probabilistic Models," the deliverable focuses on Bayesian networks as tools for assessing and enhancing the resilience of the IWT system. It explains how Bayesian networks provide a probabilistic modelling approach to capturing complex interdependencies, enabling informed decision-making in the face of uncertainties and disruptions.

Moving forward, the section "Living Labs and Generalisation" explores the concept of Living Labs as a means to validate the research findings and generalise them to real-world scenarios. This allows for the practical application of the developed ontology and models, ensuring their relevance and effectiveness in various contexts.

The deliverable concludes with the "Conclusions and Next Steps" section, summarising the key insights and implications derived from the content presented. It emphasises the value of the developed ontology and Bayesian network models in fostering sustainability and resilience within the IWT domain. Furthermore, it outlines the next steps for refining the ontology, models, and analysis techniques to drive further advancements and progress in the project.

Overall, the deliverable provides an essential foundation for the project, introducing key concepts, methods, and applications related to ontologies, Bayesian networks, and preliminary ontologies in the context of sustainable and resilient transportation planning in the Inland Waterways domain.

3 Ontologies & Knowledge Graphs

This chapter starts with presenting some of the existing studies on Ontology and knowledge graph creation. In addition, some works on using the Bayesian network for risk assessments have been reviewed. Then a presentation of Ontology and Knowledge graph is provided and in the third part, the process of constructing the ontology for the IWT resources are explained.

3.1 State of the Art

Knowledge graphs are characterized by a wide applicability ranging from modelling social networks to capturing probabilistic features of any infrastructure system. It is therefore important to consider the contextual applicability of each KG, which is achieved by simultaneously considering ontology framework to which KGs' correlate.

As an example of domain ontology creation, we can mention the work of Nandini et al. [1] in which they have developed an ontology for a semantics-aware transportation system from the perspective of a traveler user, capable of answering general competence queries like the nearest bus stop to a particular place, the nearest parking slots available, etc. In the process of ontology creation, they have followed the DERA (Domain, Entity, Relation, Attribute) [2] methodology to construct the ontology. The ontology's domain was specifically defined as "transport," and it included a well-defined set of entities representing different elements of transportation systems, such as infrastructure, modes of transport, passenger services, and logistical operations. By establishing relationships between entities, the researchers gained insights into how different transportation components interacted with each other. They explored connections between modes of transport, as well as the significance of transport nodes and their impact on overall efficiency. Attributes were incorporated into the ontology to capture essential characteristics and properties of transportation elements, such as capacity, average speed, or frequency. To facilitate knowledge sharing and interoperability with other ontologies, the researchers adhered to the Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication (MOD) standards, making the ontology more accessible to the research community for potential collaboration. In conclusion, the study provided valuable insights into transportation systems in diverse city environments. The ontology constructed using the DERA methodology with clear domain definitions, entity categorisation, established relationships, and attributes will contribute to a better understanding of urban mobility and encourage further research in the transportation domain.

In another study Zhang et al. [3] present a novel approach to understanding and analyzing Autonomous Transportation Systems (ATS) using knowledge graphs. In this work, the entity categories are defined based on five traffic elements: technology, demand, service, function and component and the correlations are established based through their attributes. They use Neo4j graph database to store and build a network knowledge graph of transportation system. They basically apply the research method of knowledge graph to construct the network knowledge graph of ATS, and visualizes its structure, laws and element distribution. In the context of ATS, the knowledge graph

includes elements such as the driver, vehicle, and roadside unit. The relationships between these elements are also represented, providing insights into how different parts of the system interact with each other. The authors apply theoretical methods to conduct an empirical analysis of the ATS. This involves using the knowledge graph to display the transportation system intuitively. Figure 7, presents an illustration of a KG of a Transportation System [3]. In this Scenario: green is for technology; pink is for demand; yellow is for function; brown is for component; purple is for service. The authors utilise intelligent knowledge co-occurrence analysis, a method that identifies and analyses the co-occurrence of different elements within the system. This method can reveal hidden patterns and relationships that might not be immediately apparent. The results of the study include the establishment of relationships between different elements of the ATS.

In the context of the T1.2.1, the methods of this study provide insights to develop an inland waterways resources KG. The knowledge graph-based network analysis can be used to decompose the inland waterways transportation system into its constituent elements and relationships. This can help in understanding the interdependencies and potential cascading effects in the system, thereby contributing to resilience-driven optimisation tools in the Digital Twin (DT).

Figure 1: Autonomous Transportation System Ontology [3]

On the risk analysis using Bayesian network, Wenhui et al. in [4] have performed inference using Bayesian network model. They have built a Bayesian network based on the data related to highway transportation accident. They have proposed knowledge inference framework for road transportation risks. Based on the Bayesian network created in their study, the probability distributions of accident occurrence were inferred under multiple factors, including the driver, vehicle, road, environment, and management. A similar ontology structure for modelling transport albeit focusing on urban transport, has been adopted by Tan et al [5].

In another recent work, Li et al [6] have incorporated the latest maritime accident data from 2017 to 2021 into a Bayesian network model to analyze the key risk influence factors in the maritime sector. They have used data of near 430 accidents for their model (out of around 1100 records).

Based on the new dataset, they have identified both dynamic and static risk influential factors (RIFs) and their new BN-based risk model can offer reliable and risk prediction results.

3.1.1 Knowledge Graphs

A Knowledge Graph is a data structure used to represent and store knowledge in a structured and interconnected manner. It consists of a collection of nodes (entities) representing real-world objects, concepts, or entities, and edges (relationships) connecting these nodes to indicate the relationships between them. The nodes and edges in a Knowledge Graph are often labelled with semantic information, which adds context and meaning to the data. They are implemented using graph databases, which are designed to handle complex relationships between entities efficiently.

3.1.2 Link between Knowledge Graphs and Ontologies

The link between Knowledge Graphs and Ontologies is that ontologies often serve as the foundational structure for constructing Knowledge Graphs. Knowledge Graphs can be seen as implementations or instantiations of ontologies, where the concepts defined in the ontology become nodes in the Knowledge Graph, and the relationships defined in the ontology become edges connecting the nodes.

3.2 Ontology Construction for IWT Resources

The ontology in its current state is a hierarchical representation of all the entities/things that constitute the domain Inland waterways. Reference 5.6.2 has been used for the development of the ontology.

The choice of entities is influenced by the objective of modelling and understanding the following performance indicators. These indicators have been identified as part of D1.1- Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks v1 and are summarised in Table 2. These will now be discussed more explicitly.

Table 2: Sustainability and Resilience indicators as identified in D1.1.

Sustainability Indicators
Economic
Environmental
Social
Resilience Indicators
Security
Safety
Knowledge Management
Visibility
Information Sharing
Trust
Risk Management
Robustness
Collaboration
Prediction Flexibility & Reaction Agility
Redundancy
Rapidity (~Responsiveness)
Resourcefulness

Figure 2: Performance Indicators scoped view of Ontology

3.2.1 Sustainability Indicators

Figure 3: Environmental Performance Indicators scoped view of Ontology

1. **Economic:** This indicator assesses the economic aspects of sustainability within a system, evaluating the financial viability and cost-effectiveness of practices or actions aimed at promoting sustainability.
2. **Environmental:** This indicator focuses on the environmental aspects of sustainability, measuring the impact of activities and policies on ecological systems, natural resources, and overall environmental health.
3. **Social:** This indicator evaluates the social dimensions of sustainability, considering factors such as community well-being, social equity, inclusivity, and the overall quality of life of individuals and societies.

3.2.2 Resilience Indicators

Figure 4: Resilience Performance Indicators scoped view of Ontology

1. **Security:** This indicator measures the level of security and protection of a system against potential threats, ensuring its ability to withstand and recover from adverse events without compromising safety.
2. **Safety:** This indicator assesses the safety measures and practices in place to prevent accidents, incidents, or hazards, and to ensure the protection of assets, individuals, and the environment.
3. **Knowledge Management:** This indicator focuses on the effective management and utilisation of knowledge and information within a system to enhance decision-making, problem-solving, and overall system performance.
4. **Visibility:** This indicator measures the extent to which a system can effectively monitor and perceive its internal and external conditions, enabling timely awareness and response to changes or disruptions.
5. **Information Sharing:** This indicator evaluates the efficiency and effectiveness of sharing relevant information and data among stakeholders to enhance collaboration, coordination, and decision-making processes.

6. **Trust:** This indicator assesses the level of trust and confidence among stakeholders in sharing information, knowledge, and decision-making responsibilities to promote collective resilience.
7. **Risk Management:** This indicator measures the effectiveness of risk assessment, mitigation, and management strategies within a system to anticipate and address potential risks and vulnerabilities.
8. **Robustness:** This indicator evaluates the system's ability to maintain stable and reliable performance under varying conditions, minimising disruptions and ensuring consistent functionality.
9. **Collaboration:** This indicator assesses the level of cooperation and collaboration among stakeholders within a system to achieve common resilience goals and foster collective problem-solving.
10. **Flexibility (prediction) & Agility (reaction):** This indicator measures the system's capacity to anticipate changes, adapt swiftly, and respond effectively to dynamic and unforeseen circumstances.
11. **Redundancy:** This indicator evaluates the existence and effectiveness of backup systems or resources to ensure continued functionality and resilience in case of failures or disruptions.
12. **Rapidity (~ Responsiveness):** This indicator assesses the system's responsiveness and quick reaction time in identifying and addressing emerging challenges or critical incidents.
13. **Resourcefulness:** This indicator evaluates the ability of the system to creatively and effectively utilize available resources to overcome challenges and maintain functionality during adverse conditions.

3.2.3 IWT Domain Entities

In the IWT domain there exist several entities which need to be captured by the ontology. We have abstracted these into several high-level categories (classes of entities). The top-level classes for the entities involved in IWT are summarized in Table 3 and are discussed more explicitly further in this Section.

Table 3: Top-level classes for IWT entities

Class		
Actions	Hazards	Identifiers
Infrastructure	Locations	Measurements
Operations	Performance Indicators	Personnel
Ports	Propulsion Systems	Regulations
Sensors	Vessels	Waterways

These classes encompass the broad range of elements that interact within the complex system of inland waterways. They provide a structured framework for representing and analysing the multifaceted components and activities within the system. This classification is based on the current understanding of the domain that the project partners have of the expected IWT system within ReNEW and aims to encapsulate the core aspects that define the functioning and characteristics of inland waterways pertaining to the project. As our understanding of the system deepens and evolves, these classes can be further specialised and restructured or re-evaluated to better model the dynamics of the system. The ontology, with these top-level classes at its core, forms an essential tool for understanding, analysing, and potentially predicting cascading effects within the intricate system of ReNEW.

Figure 5: Top level entity classes of ontology

1. **Actions:** Represents various actions or activities within the inland waterways system. Actions could include navigation, docking, loading/unloading of cargo, and maintenance operations.
2. **Hazards:** Encompasses all potential dangers or risks within the inland waterways. These can be environmental (storms, high water levels), technical (equipment failure), or operational (human error).
3. **Identifiers:** Identifiers are unique tags or labels assigned to specific entities within the system. These entities could be vessels, personnel, infrastructure, or locations.

4. **Infrastructure:** Refers to the crucial physical structures that facilitate the functioning of inland waterways. This includes but is not limited to ports, locks, bridges, and channels.
5. **Locations:** Specific geographic points within the inland waterways system. They can be sections of a waterway, ports, or cities.
6. **Measurements:** Measurements are quantifiable metrics in the inland waterways context. These can be related to various operational parameters such as water depth, vessel speed, or cargo weight.
7. **Operations:** Represent the various procedural aspects of inland waterways. This includes processes such as vessel navigation, cargo handling, and infrastructure maintenance.
8. **Performance Indicators:** Metrics used to assess the performance or effectiveness of different aspects of inland waterways. They can measure vessel efficiency, infrastructure reliability, safety standards, and more.
9. **Personnel:** The personnel class encompasses individuals who have various roles within the inland waterways system. This can include roles such as captains, crew members, port staff, and regulators.
10. **Ports:** Specialised facilities where vessels can dock to load or unload cargo, undergo maintenance, refuel, and perform other necessary operations.
11. **Propulsion Systems:** The propulsion systems class covers the systems that propel vessels within inland waterways. These systems can range from different types of engines and propellers to non-motorised methods like sailing.
12. **Regulations:** involves the rules and standards that govern the operation of inland waterways. These regulations cover navigation rules, safety standards, and environmental protection guidelines.
13. **Sensors:** Sensors are devices used to monitor various parameters within the inland waterways system. These can measure environmental conditions, vessel performance, infrastructure status, among other things.
14. **Vessels:** Vessels are waterborne crafts that operate within the inland waterways. This class can include cargo ships, barges, tugboats, passenger vessels, and others.
15. **Waterways:** The waterways class represents the actual navigable waters that vessels travel on. This includes rivers, canals, and other types of waterways.

3.2.4 Infrastructure

In the current version of the ontology, the following components have been identified and the relationships mapped as shown in the following image.

Figure 6: Infrastructure entity classes of Ontology

Figure 7: Relationships of entities shown in Figure 6

1. **Rip-Rap:** Riprap is rock or other material used to armor shorelines, streambeds, bridge abutments, pilings and other shoreline structures against scour and water, wave, or ice erosion. It's used to protect the banks of rivers and other waterways from erosion.
2. **Lock:** A lock is a device used for raising and lowering boats, ships and other watercraft between stretches of water of different levels on river and canal waterways. Locks are used to make a river more easily navigable, or to allow a canal to cross land that is not level.
3. **Longitudinal Dike:** A longitudinal dike is a structure built parallel to the flow of a river, typically on its banks, to regulate the flow of water and prevent flooding or erosion. It helps in channelizing the river flow and is an important part of inland waterways infrastructure.
4. **Communication Network:** this refers to the system of devices, software, and protocols used to coordinate and communicate between different parts of the waterway system. This could include communication between ships, locks, loading systems, and control centers.
5. **Chevron:** In the context of waterways, a chevron is a V-shaped marking which is usually used on navigation signs or buoys to guide vessels and indicate safe or navigable channels.
6. **Training Walls:** Training walls are structures built within a water body to direct its flow in a certain path. They are used to control the water flow to prevent erosion, sedimentation, and to improve navigability.
7. **Groynes:** Groynes are rigid hydraulic structures built from an ocean shore or a bank in rivers, that interrupt water flow and limit the movement of sediment. In the ocean, they create beaches, or avoid having them washed away by longshore drift.
8. **Loading Systems:** These are systems used for loading and unloading cargo from ships. They can range from simple manual systems to highly automated systems.
9. **Landing Site:** In the context of inland waterways, a landing site is a place where boats or ships can come to shore to load or unload cargo and passengers.

10. **Shores (River bank):** The shore or shoreline is the fringe of land at the edge of a large body of water, such as an ocean, sea, or lake.
11. **Bridges:** A bridge is a structure built to span a physical obstacle, such as a body of water, for the purpose of providing passage over the obstacle.
12. **Overdepth:** refers to the additional depth to which an area is dredged. This is done to ensure that the specified navigable depth is maintained over time as natural processes deposit sediment into the dredged area.
13. **Sills:** in the context of waterways, a sill is the submerged threshold or base of a lock or weir, or the bottom of the entrance to a canal from a river, below the lock gates, over which vessels must pass.
14. **Scour Hole:** A scour hole is a depression or hole in a body of water caused by the water's erosive action. This can occur in rivers, around bridge pilings, and other areas where water flow is disrupted.

3.2.5 Relationships

To achieve the objectives of understanding, predicting and simulating various aspects of sustainability and resilience as measured with the potentially calculable KPIs listed in the corresponding section for performance indicators using the knowledge graphs, the relationships between the entities are to be captured along with constituent entities themselves. Just as the entities, the relationships can be encoded in a hierarchical structure.

In the current ontology, some high level relationships are captured such as:

Controls:

Relationship type "controls" can capture the relationship between imposed regulation and action entities. Regulations influences actions. Prohibition of wastewater disposal for example.

Exists_on:

Relationship type "Exists_on" captures the spatial or locational relationship between two entities. It indicates that one entity is physically present or situated on another entity. For example, in a sustainability context, this relationship can be used to represent the location of certain resources, facilities, or infrastructure in specific geographic areas or regions. For instance, "Wind turbines exist_on Wind Farm A" implies that the wind turbines are physically located on Wind Farm A.

Has individual:

The "Has individual" relationship is used to express the connection between a collective group or class and its individual members or instances. In the context of sustainability and resilience, this relationship can be employed to show the specific entities that belong to a particular category or

group. For example, "Sustainable Buildings has individual Building X, Building Y, and Building Z" indicates that Building X, Building Y, and Building Z are specific instances of sustainable buildings.

Has subclass:

The "Has subclass" relationship represents a hierarchical relationship between classes or categories in an ontology. It indicates that one class is a more specialised or specific subcategory of another class. In the domain of sustainability and resilience, this relationship can be utilised to establish hierarchical classifications of concepts. For instance, "Renewable Energy has subclass Solar Energy, Wind Energy, and Hydro Energy" implies that Solar Energy, Wind Energy, and Hydro Energy are specific subcategories of Renewable Energy.

Occurs_on:

The "Occurs_on" relationship denotes a temporal relationship between two entities, where an event or activity takes place on a specific date, time, or within a certain period. In the context of sustainability and resilience, this relationship can be used to represent the occurrence of various events or incidents on specific dates or timeframes. For example, "Natural Disaster Occurs_on 2023-07-26" indicates that the natural disaster event occurred on the date July 26, 2023.

Operate:

The "Operate" relationship captures the operational connection between two entities, typically indicating that one entity is responsible for operating or managing another entity. In the context of sustainability and resilience, this relationship can be utilised to represent the operation of various systems or processes. For example, "Water Treatment Plant operates Water Distribution System" implies that the Water Treatment Plant is responsible for operating the Water Distribution System.

Performed on:

The "Performed on" relationship describes the connection between an action or activity and the entity on which the action is carried out. In the context of sustainability and resilience, this relationship can be used to represent actions performed on specific targets or subjects. For example, "Maintenance Activity Performed on Solar Panels" indicates that the Maintenance Activity is carried out on the Solar Panels.

Port equipped with:

The "Port equipped with" relationship signifies that a port or harbour is equipped with specific facilities, resources, or infrastructure. In the context of sustainability and resilience, this relationship can be used to represent the assets and amenities available at a port to support its operations. For instance, "Port A equipped with Crane, Warehouse, and Cold Storage" implies that Port A has the infrastructure of Crane, Warehouse, and Cold Storage facilities.

4 Network Analysis and Probabilistic Models

4.1 Resilience and Probabilistic Modelling through Bayesian Networks

Digital twin models can be physics-based, statistical-based or hybrid. In the ReNEW project, Bayesian networks are proposed in order to build probabilistic decision module which are capable of mathematically representing the high-level dependencies in IWT infrastructure. Using field data and expert opinion, Bayesian Networks are used to model the interdependencies between system components. As new (field) data becomes available through monitoring and other remote data, the Bayesian Network Model can be updated, resulting in more accurate estimates.

In this section, a brief overview of Bayesian Networks will be provided along with a theoretical example in order to provide the context for ReNEW partners. This is considered the first step in developing Bayesian Networks for one or more of the ReNEW Living Labs.

Bayesian Networks (BNs) are a type of Probabilistic Graphical Model that can be used to build models from data and/or expert opinion. They can be used for a wide range of tasks including diagnostics, reasoning, causal modelling, decision making under uncertainty, anomaly detection, automated insight and prediction.

A BN comprises two components: the qualitative component and the quantitative component. A BN's qualitative component is a graphical representation of the interdependencies among variables in a system. Associated with them are a set of functions representing numerical quantities. Every node in the graph is associated with a probability function, which represents a collection of conditional probabilities expressing how the predecessors impacted the node's probability.

A graphical representation of a BN is illustrated in Figure 9. The network is a collection of nodes that represent objects, variables or elements in a system, and links that represent their relationships. Each node has a certain number of states representing the condition of each element of the infrastructure. The state of Node D is probabilistically dependent upon the state of node B, which in turn is also dependent on the state of node A.

Figure 8: A graphical representation of a BN with its components

In order to illustrate the graphs further, a Bayesian network for evaluating the risk of bridge failure due to scour is illustrated in Figure 10. At the top of the graph are various properties of the river beneath the bridge (velocity, depth, discharge) as well as the bridge itself (abutment shape coefficient, skew coefficient). The state of each of these nodes impacts the following nodes, which indicate the probability of various states of local scour failure and contraction scour failure, at either a pier or abutment of the bridge.

Figure 9: Bayesian Network for calculating bridge failure. (Probabilities are omitted)

The initial nodes in the graph may be considered “trigger” nodes, since they are not dependent on any other parts of the system. An example of the internal dynamics of the “Depth” node is illustrated in Table 1. For simplicity, only two states are investigated (river depth less than 1.0, and river depth greater than 1.0). The probability of this node being in state 1 is 0.9, for the given analysis.

Table 4: Local Dynamics of “Depth” node

State	Meaning	Probability
1	$D < 1.0\text{m}$	0.9
2	$D \geq 1.0\text{m}$	0.1

The “Depth” node then impacts the node for “Contraction scour at pier” (among others), This node is also impacted by the “Discharge” node and the node “Model correction factor for contraction scour depth”. Assuming each of these nodes to only have two possible states, Table 2 illustrates the local

dynamics for the node “contraction scour at pier”. It can be seen that as the condition of the preceding nodes worsen (increase), the probability of being in a higher level of contraction scour also increases. This node then impacts the possibility of failure at the pier, represented by the node “failure due to contraction and local scour at pier”.

Table 5: Local Dynamics of “Contraction scour at pier” node

Depth State	Discharge State	Correction factor state	Contraction Scour at pier level 1	Contraction Scour at pier level 2	Contraction Scour at pier level 3
1	1	1	0.9	0.1	0.0
1	2	1	0.8	0.2	0.0
1	1	2	0.7	0.2	0.1
1	2	2	0.6	0.3	0.1
2	1	1	0.5	0.3	0.2
2	2	1	0.4	0.4	0.2
2	1	2	0.3	0.4	0.3
2	2	2	0.2	0.4	0.4

Table 6: Local Dynamics of “Failure due to contraction and local scour at pier” node

Contraction Scour at Pier	Local Scour at Pier	Failure?	No Failure?
1	1	0.0	1.0
1	2	0.1	0.9
1	3	0.2	0.8
2	1	0.3	0.7
2	2	0.4	0.6
2	3	0.5	0.5
3	1	0.6	0.4
3	2	0.7	0.3
3	3	0.8	0.2

The final node relating to bridge failure is then considered a binary node, as per Table 4.

Table 7: Local Dynamics of “Bridge Failure” node

Failure due to contraction and local scour at abutment	Failure due to contraction and local scour at pier	Bridge failure?	No Bridge Failure
0	0	0	1
1	0	1	0
0	1	1	0
0	1	1	0

The final output of this theoretical BN would provide a probability of bridge failure due to scour. This can then be built into a risk/resilience assessment calculation based on calculating the consequences associated with each scour event. It should be noted that mitigation measures can also be investigated. For example, in the theoretical example illustrated, one can investigate different properties of “rip-wrap” application to the abutments which would reduce the probabilities of scour failure. Mitigation actions can also be input as a deterministic variable to analyse separate cases of mitigation.

In order to develop BNs for the ReNEW LLs, a semantic ontology is first required similar to the PRECINCT knowledge graphs. In order to define this, the following stepwise methodology is proposed.

1. Determine the overall “risk” and/or “service measures” associated with the LL. That is, what is the service that can be impacted due to unforeseen breakdown, and what are the consequences of this breakdown.
2. Determine the various primary infrastructure networks and objects that are required to keep the service in place.
3. Determine the infrastructure sub-elements that impact each part of the network and objects.
4. Model the various interdependencies with qualitative links.

Once this qualitative graph has been defined, local dynamics for each node are required. It is proposed that in the first instance, the graphs will be populated with probabilities based on expert knowledge determined through workshops with the LL participants. Various methods are available to optimise this process. It is proposed in ReNEW to adopt quantitative estimation in a manner similar to Konig and Shaaban [7], which not only provides a framework which encourages feedback from experts, but also allows quantification of uncertainty.

Once the initial local dynamics are entered into the BN, it will be used to perform risk and resilience assessment in accordance with ReNEW Task 1.1. Subsequently, further workshops will be carried out with the LL leaders to determine where more refined probabilistic models can be used based on monitoring and sensor data.

5 Living Labs and Framework Generalisation

The "Infrastructure Resilience Interdependencies and Cascading Effects Knowledge Graphs" task is an initiative that leverages the advantages of Knowledge Graphs to enhance the resilience and green operation of Inland Water Transport (IWT). This Knowledge Graph, which provides a structured and interconnected representation of data, is instrumental in the operation of four distinct Living Labs (LLs), each with a unique focus. The aim of the task is to address the needs of each Living Lab and at the same time establish the building blocks for an integrated and generalised Framework for representing IWT and for analysing its cascading effects.

5.1 ReNEW Living Labs

5.1.1 Living Lab #1 - Ghent's Multifunctional Sychromodality City Logistics Hub

LL1 is centred on the evaluation of climate disasters' impact on infrastructure resilience and the readiness of emergency plans. The application of Knowledge Graphs in this context provides a comprehensive, interconnected overview of Ghent's infrastructure. This includes an understanding of the various components, their interdependencies, and vulnerabilities to different types of climate disasters. This interconnected data representation aids city planners and emergency response teams in identifying potential weak points in the infrastructure, thereby informing strategies to enhance resilience.

Moreover, Knowledge Graphs facilitate the modelling of various disaster scenarios and their potential impacts on the city's infrastructure. This predictive capability provides valuable insights for the development of emergency plans, ensuring their effectiveness and targeted response. The continuous updating of the Knowledge Graphs with real-time data allows for the dynamic monitoring and evaluation of the city's infrastructure resilience and emergency plans, enabling necessary adjustments based on current data.

5.1.2 Living Lab #2 – Smart Douro Inland Waterway management – DIW2024

LL2 aims to enhance the overall performance of the Douro river transportation system. In this context, Knowledge Graphs serve as a detailed representation of the Douro river transportation system, including its various components (vessels, ports, navigation aids), their interconnections, and operational parameters (speed, capacity, schedule). This comprehensive view aids system operators in understanding the system's dynamics and identifying potential bottlenecks or inefficiencies.

Knowledge Graphs also facilitate the modelling and analysis of different operational scenarios, such as changes in traffic volume, disruptions due to weather conditions, or the implementation of new navigation technologies. This analytical capability supports decision-making and strategic planning,

contributing to the enhancement of the system's safety, security, environmental protection, and navigation efficiency. The integration of data from various sources into the Knowledge Graphs provides a comprehensive and up-to-date view of the system's status, enabling quick and informed responses to any emerging issues or challenges.

5.1.3 Living Lab #3 - Planning mitigation demonstrator app for climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, and in addition to boost modal shift

LL3 is developing a mitigation demonstrator app to promote climate resilience and environmental sustainability in transport infrastructure and boost modal shift towards sustainable transport options. In this context, Knowledge Graphs provide a structured and interconnected representation of the transport infrastructure, including its various components (roads, bridges, railways, ports), their environmental impacts (emissions, noise, habitat disruption), and their vulnerabilities to climate change (flooding, heat stress, sea-level rise). This comprehensive view informs the development of the mitigation demonstrator app, identifying critical issues and opportunities for improvement.

Knowledge Graphs also facilitate the modelling and analysis of different mitigation strategies and their potential impacts on climate resilience and environmental sustainability. This analytical capability informs the design of the app's features and functions, ensuring it effectively supports users in making informed and sustainable transport decisions. The integration of user feedback and usage data into the Knowledge Graphs allows for the monitoring and evaluation of the app's effectiveness and impact, identifying areas for improvement and tracking its contribution to promoting climate resilience and environmental sustainability in transport infrastructure and boosting modal shift.

5.1.4 Living Lab #4 – Resilience promoting Autonomous zero-emissions barges

LL4 is focused on promoting resilience through autonomous, zero-emission barges. In this context, Knowledge Graphs serve as a detailed representation of the operational parameters and environmental impacts of the autonomous, zero-emission barges. This comprehensive view aids in understanding their performance, identifying potential issues or challenges, and developing strategies to enhance their resilience and effectiveness.

Knowledge Graphs also facilitate the modelling and analysis of different operational scenarios for the autonomous, zero-emission barges, such as changes in traffic volume, disruptions due to weather conditions, or the implementation of new navigation technologies. This analytical capability supports decision-making and strategic planning, helping to optimise the barges' operations and minimise their environmental impacts. The integration of data from various sources into the Knowledge Graphs provides a comprehensive and up-to-date view of the barges' status, enabling quick and informed responses to any emerging issues or challenges.

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, the Knowledge Graphs developed in the "Infrastructure Resilience Interdependencies and Cascading Effects Knowledge Graphs" project final deliverable provides each Living Lab with a powerful tool for data representation, analysis, and decision-making. This contributes to the overall goal of the project: to enhance the resilience and green operation of Inland Water Transport (IWT), thereby addressing the risks and hazards posed by climate change and network disruptions.

6 Next Steps

There are several unknowns at this stage in achieving the objectives of developing the most relevant and complete Ontology and subsequently the development of methods and algorithms to complete Tasks 1.2.2 and 1.2.3. Considering that, the following is plan towards completing T1.2

1. Iterative Ontological Refinement through Living Labs

- Schedule and conduct recurring consultations, workshops, and collaborative sessions with Living Labs.
- Utilize the gathered feedback for ontology refinement and validation.

2. Neo4j Database Implementation

- Formulate and implement the database schema grounded in the finalized ontology.
- Undertake a rigorous validation process to ensure the database's reliability and efficiency.

3. Data Population Strategy

- Curate, normalize, and integrate empirical data from Living Labs into the Neo4j database, adhering to the ontological framework.

4. Development of Specialized Queries and Algorithms

- Engineer specialized queries and algorithms that are congruent with the objectives outlined in Task T1.2.
- Systematically explore methodologies such as Graph Query Languages, Graph Algorithms, Probabilistic models, Bayesian Networks and Graph Analytics for addressing specific KPIs.

7 Conclusion

In the context of the ReNEW project, deliverable D1.4 focuses on the specific scope of Task 1.2, which entails the development of Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs (KGs) for analyzing IWT infrastructure resilience, interdependencies, and cascading effects. Existing ontologies in the domain had formats incompatible with the project's objectives, which necessitated the creation of a uniquely tailored ontology. Public data to enrich the project has been scarce and hard to access, making the KG primarily dependent on limited datasets. The primary goal of Task 1.2 was not merely the construction of a KG but also the integration of AI & ML algorithms to facilitate data-driven risk analysis and cost-optimization. These algorithms are built to handle the intricacies of risk factors and their potential cascading effects on IWT infrastructure.

The ontology developed under Task 1.2 is in its early stages but serves as a pivotal element in enabling the KG's functionalities. Even in its nascent form, it is configured to be extensible and adaptable, opening avenues for future updates and refinements. The KG aims at a twofold utility: first, as a tool for stakeholders to receive insights into the resilience and risk factors associated with IWT, and second, as a platform to engage stakeholders in understanding the interconnected aspects of IWT systems. Future iterations of this work could involve rigorous iterative testing of AI & ML methodologies to further refine the ontology and the KG, potentially expanding its applicability to other transport infrastructures. These elements collectively contribute to laying a foundational framework, thereby fulfilling the objectives of Task 1.2 as outlined in D1.4, and setting a trajectory for future research and applications in IWT infrastructure resilience.

8 References

- [1] D. Nandini et al., 2018. An Ontology for Transportation System. RuleML+RR: 2018 2nd International Joint Conference on Rules and Reasoning, 18-21 Sep 2018, Luxembourg.
- [2] F. Giunchiglia et al., 2011. A faceted knowledge organization framework. Technical report, University of Trento, 2011.
- [3] L. Zhang et al. Knowledge Graph-based Network Analysis on the Elements of Autonomous Transportation System, 2021
- [4] L. Wenhui et al. Bayesian Network-Based Knowledge Graph Inference for Highway Transportation Safety Risks, 2021
- [5] J. Tan et al. Research on the construction of a Knowledge Graph and Knowledge Reasoning Model in the Field of Urban Traffic, 2021
- [6] Huanhuan Li et al. Data-driven Bayesian network for risk analysis of global maritime accidents, Engineering & System Safety journal, 2023
- [7] König, S., & Shaaban, A. M. (2022, August). Parametrization of Probabilistic Risk Models. In Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security (pp. 1-6).